

MCAM – Parental Behavior

Parental Behavior	Description
Parent Positive	
1. Sensitivity	The parent recognizes and understands the signals of the child and reacts adequately.
a. <u>Attention</u> and behavior directed towards the child	<p>The parent is aware of the signals of the child. The parent is not only focused on his/her thoughts or activities.</p> <p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbally encouraging (e.g., “hmm”, “yes”, “I see.”) • Paraphrasing <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The parent looks at the child/makes eye contact. • Encouraging gesture (e.g., nodding) • Open posture
b. <u>Responsivity</u> : Clear perception and adequate responsiveness to the social and emotional expressions of the child.	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection of feelings (e.g., If the child is sad because the task fails, the parent peeks in and mirrors it verbally: “I see that you are sad.”) • Reaction to a question: The parent meets the request of the child (e.g., if the child asks for the map with the original set up, the parent passes it) • The parent poses a question aiming to understand the preference, needs, or state of the child and/or to meet the needs. (e.g., “Do you want me to help? Would you like to stop?”) • The parent reassures the child (e.g., “Sorry, I was still busy. This is a difficult exercise.”).
c. Positive affective communication (<u>PAC</u>)	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive assumptions about the child: The parent addresses the child in a non-directive way, that includes a positive assumption about the child, his/her preferences, intentions, behavior, or situation (e.g., “You had a good day”; “You are Ok.”; “You can fix it.”; or “You already tried a lot!”). • Praise: A positive, evaluative, or descriptive remark about the child, or his/her attitude or task participation (e.g., “Good boy/girl”; “I love you”). • Humor: The parent makes a playful, creative, or humorous remark to the child.

	<p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laughing, Smiling • Positive physical contact (e.g., stroking the arm of the child, patting their shoulder, giving a hug or kiss)
<p>2. Structuring (positive /task-related)</p>	<p>The parent structures the behavior of the child by giving instructions, making rules, and defining limits and borders for the child.</p>
<p>a. <u>Structure</u> behavior in a <u>positive</u> way</p>	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demanding a certain behavior: The parent commands or tells the child directly to conduct in a certain way (e.g., “Sit down on your chair”; “Please, leave the wires in place”; “Stay calm and keep your seat”) • Requesting a certain behavior: The parent tells the child or asks the child gently to conduct in a certain way (e.g., “Would you mind staying away from these wires?”, “Let’s try to sit quietly”). • Attention prompt: The parent poses a verbal prompt, aiming to gain the visual or auditory attention of the child (e.g., “Look!”, “Listen!”). • Verbal model as prompt for verbal imitation: The parent offers the child a verbal model of what he/she thinks the child would have to say aiming to let the child imitate the behavior. (e.g., parent says “Thank you”, as the child is expected to say “Thank you” in this situation.). • Tangible extrinsic reinforcement for the child: The parent gives/promises the child a desired item or activity (e.g., “You get candy from me.”). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nonverbal prompt: Parent informs child in a nonverbal way what he/she expects the child to do (e.g., tapping on the chair to indicate that the child needs to sit down).
<p>b. <u>Task-related structuring</u></p>	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demanding a task-related behavior: The parent commands the child or tells him/her directly to perform a certain task-related behavior (e.g., “Put the car here”; “No, slide this car to the other side”; “You need to slide the car towards the border”). • Requesting a task-related behavior: The parent asks or tells the child gently to perform a certain task-related behavior (e.g., “Let’s try to solve the puzzle.”, “Wouldn’t you better slide the car in this direction?”, “Why don’t you try this move?”).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task informative prompt: The parent informs the child implicitly that the child is expected to continue or restart working on the task (e.g., "It's your turn.>"). • The parent invites the child to think about the task (e.g., by discussing the next steps or asking questions concerning the task). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nonverbal prompt: Parent displays nonverbal behavior to inform the child what they are expected to do regarding the task (e.g., tapping on the table near the puzzle to indicate that the child needs to keep their attention on the puzzle, pointing at the place where the child should slide the car).
Parent Negative	
3. Structuring in a directive, negative way	The parent structures the behavior of the child by giving instructions, making rules, or defining limits for the child.
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disapproval/reprimand (or scolding): The parent makes a non-directive statement to the child, which communicates disapproval of his/her behavior. The tone can vary from neutral to negative (e.g., "That was not nice", "That is not allowed"). When reprimanding, the tone is always negative (such as harsh, critical, sarcastic) (e.g., "No, no, no!"). • Note: The child must have done something in advance that is not allowed. The parent, therefore, does not reprimand/disapprove without cause. • Negative contingency or threat: The parent tells the child that he/she can't /won't get something pleasant. This can take the form of a contingency statement (e.g., "Don't cheat or you won't get movie tickets."), a question that takes the form of a threat (e.g., "Do you want to be punished?"), or a statement about something unpleasant that will be administered (e.g., "You will go to bed an hour earlier.>"). • Negative question: The parent asks the child a question that is negative in meaning and/or intonation (e.g., "Have you cheated?!"). <p>Negative statement: The parent makes a neutral statement in content, but has a clear negative or disapproving undertone (e.g., "Kate!", "No!", "I came here especially today!").</p>

	<p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical withdrawal/control of problem behavior (e.g., physically guiding the child back to his place, holding the child's hands so that he cannot hit; if the child wants to use an object for problem behavior, push or hold the object). All this is done in a non-aggressive manner.
4. Hostility	The general emotional climate is hostile. The parent expresses anger, negativity, boredom, or rejection of the child.
a. <u>Covert</u> hostility	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The parent expresses being bored. The parent verbalizes impatience. The parent raises his/her voice. The parent puffs, sighs. The parent swears (e.g., "For goodness sake, I hate that game!"). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The parent rolls his eyes. The parent taps his/her fingers on the table. <p><i>Note: This hostility does not necessarily have to be directed towards the child.</i></p>
b. <u>Overt</u> hostility	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The parent makes fun of the child. The parent gets angry at the child. The parent depreciates the child (e.g., "You can't do anything right!"). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The parent hits the table. The parent kicks against a chair. Negative physical contact (e.g., grasps the child's arm, hits, squeezes a part of the child's body, pulls the ears) <p><i>Note: The parental behavior is frightening and threatening to the child.</i></p>
5. Non-contingent reaction	<p>A parent's response that does not match the child's question, need, or behavior.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The parent does not respond though the child asks for this (e.g., the child is crying, but the parent does not respond). The parent's reaction does not fit the situation (e.g., the parent just laughs, while the child expresses frustration).

MCAM – Child Behavior

Child Behavior	Description
Child positive	
1. Responsivity	'Child responsiveness' refers to the degree of social and emotional responsiveness of the child towards the parent.
a. <u>Engagement</u> in the relation with the parent	<p>The child's willingness to participate in the interaction with the parent, following a question or invitation to interact, and the child's degree of obedience</p> <p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The child answers a parent's question appropriately. • The child accepts the parent's invitation to dialogue. • The child obeys a demand/request: After the parent makes a request, the child complies with this request. <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The child does not resist positive physical contact initiated by the parent. • The child obeys when the parent prevents, stops, or constrains the physical problem behavior of the child; the child shows no physical resistance to the parent's intervention, and the child stops problem behavior. <p><i>Note: An interaction invitation from the parent needs to precede the child's behavior.</i></p>
b. <u>Affective</u> positive	<p>The child shows clear signals of pleasure in the interaction.</p> <p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive assumption: The child makes a positive comment about the parent (e.g., "I enjoy it that you help me."). • Praise: The child makes a positive, evaluative statement to the parent, including expressions of appreciation and affection (e.g., "Thank you!", "I love you.", "Good, Mom."). • Humor: The child makes a playful, creative, or humorous comment towards the parent. <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laughing, smiling <p><i>Note: This laughter shows the fun in the interaction (not laughing out of a certain nervousness, for example).</i></p>

2. Child <u>involves</u> parent (the subject is neutral or <u>positive</u>)	The child involves the parent in the interaction and/or the activity.
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand: The child directly tells the parent to perform a certain behavior that is appropriate in the given context (e.g., during the puzzle-solving process, the child says: "Give me the map of the initial car positions."). • Request: The child asks the parent to engage in certain behavior that is appropriate in the context in question (e.g., "Can you help me?"). • Neutral assumption: The child makes a neutral statement to the parent (e.g., "If I move the car there, they get stuck again."). • Parent-directed question: The child asks the parent a neutral or conversational question (e.g., "What time is it?") • Positive question about the parent's wishes or needs: The child asks the parent about his/her interests, wishes, or needs (e.g., "Do you like the game?"). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The child looks at the parent, seeking eye contact. • The child shows the activity/game to the parent (e.g., the child moves the puzzle towards the mother). • Positive contact: The child initiates positive, affective physical contact with the parent (e.g., a kiss, a hug). • Physical Prompt: The child makes a gesture that clearly and unambiguously shows that the child desires the parent to engage in a behavior that is appropriate in the particular context (e.g., the child "waves" at the parent to signal that he/she has to come).
Child Negative	
3. Child <u>involves</u> parent (content is <u>negative</u>)	The child involves the parent in the interaction and/or his/her activity.
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The child comments with a clear negative message (e.g., "I hate this game."). • The child asks a question with a clear negative message (e.g., "When can we stop this stupid game?"). • The child verbally expresses his/her dissatisfaction with the situation (e.g., sighing, puffing). • The child shows his/her dissatisfaction with the situation by raising his/her voice.

	<p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The child shows his/her dissatisfaction with the situation in a nonverbal way (e.g., hitting the table with the hand, waving the hand wildly in the air, crying). <p><i>Note: This subcategory concerns the content/message that is negative. When the negativity is directed towards the parent, it should be coded under the category of "proximity and interaction avoidance behavior".</i></p>
<p>4. <u>Controlling contact maintaining</u> behavior</p>	<p>When the parent leaves/wants to leave, the child clings to the parent. The child tries to maintain closeness to the parent.</p>
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The child tells the parent not to leave (e.g., "You have to keep helping me; I can't do it alone."). The child asks the parent not to leave (e.g., "Will you please stay here to help me?"; "Will you help me because I can't do it alone?"). The child demands that the parent stays with him/her (e.g., "Don't go back!"). <p><i>Note: You should only code this behavior if the tone is fearful. The intonation of the voice should express concern.</i></p> <p>Non-verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The child holds the parent's hand when he/she wants to leave. The child clings to the parent. The child pulls (gently) at the parent's clothes.
<p>5. <u>Proximity and interaction avoidant</u> behavior</p>	<p>The child avoids interaction with the parent. He/she will not attempt to interact nor accurately respond to the parent's initiatives (The tone is rather neutral).</p>
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The child gives a very short (blunt) answer to a question from the parent. The child does not answer a question from the parent (neither verbally nor nonverbally). <p><i>Note: This behavior should only be coded if the parent has clearly asked a question that is expected to receive a response.</i></p> <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The child avoids eye contact. The child adopts a disinterested attitude. The child turns away from the parent. The child looks in the other direction.

<p>6. Proximity and interaction <u>resisting behavior</u></p>	<p>The child actively resists the interaction with the parent (the tone is rather aggressive and angry).</p>
	<p>Verbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal aggression, including swearing, threatening, and criticism: The child's negative verbal communication towards the parent causes stress to the parent, such as name-calling (e.g., "Bitch!"), threatening (e.g., "I'm going to break this !"), criticism (e.g., "I hate you!"), sarcasm (e.g., "Thank you, Mom!"). • Inappropriate verbal demands or requests: The child makes a request or demand that is not appropriate given the circumstances (e.g., "Be quiet!", "Go away, you can't do anything, can you?"). • The child yells or rants at the parent. • The child speaks to the parent in an irritated tone (e.g., "But Mommy...!", "You can see that that's impossible!"). <p>Nonverbal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The child resists parental attempts to make positive physical contact (e.g. pushing the parent's hand away when he is trying to help). • Physical aggression: The child makes negative physical contact with the parent causing stress or pain to the parent (e.g., hitting, kicking, spitting, pulling). • The child offers physical resistance to physical help or hindrance from the parent (e.g., pushing the parent away; 'escaping' from the parent's grasp, grabbing the parent's arm to stop him/her). <p><i>Note: Behavior under this category should be openly parent-oriented.</i></p>

Task-related behavior

<p>Working on the puzzle</p>	
<p>a. <u>Parent</u> works <u>alone</u></p>	<p>The parent works on the puzzle alone.</p>
<p>b. <u>Child</u> works <u>alone</u></p>	<p>The child works on the puzzle alone.</p>
<p>c. Child and parent work <u>together</u></p>	<p>Child and parent work on the puzzle at the same moment.</p>